

PRINCIPALS' INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISION PRACTICE AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined how principals' instructional supervision practice predicts the job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Theory X and Theory Y were used to guide the study. One research question and a corresponding null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 254 school principals and 7388 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The sample was 739 teachers from the three Senatorial Districts, selected through the clustered sampling technique. Two research instruments tagged "Principals' Instructional Supervision Practice Questionnaire" (PISPQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The questionnaires were administered and the data generated in this study were analysed using Simple Linear Regression analysis. The research hypothesis was tested at a .05 level of significance. The results showed that principals' instructional supervision practice significantly predicts teachers' job performance in lesson preparation, lesson delivery, classroom management, use of instructional materials and students' assessment in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that principals should personally conduct instructional supervision occasionally to ascertain the level of effectiveness of instructional supervision by their subordinates. Likewise, the Ministry of Education and State Secondary Education Board should as a matter of priority ensure that principals who are appointed to head schools have the administrative leadership capacities for smooth and effective supervision of the public secondary schools' teachers.

1.1 Introduction

The attainment of the goals of an educational institution is of concern to all the stakeholders. Considering the nature of man, if the authorities of the educational institutions especially in Nigerian secondary schools fail to effectively carry out their administrative duties, teachers may be ineffective thereby leading to poor performance of students in the public secondary schools. In the administration of secondary schools, the principal is central. The principal is the man at the helm of the

affairs who receives all praises when success is attained and blames when the school fails. According to Ogundele, Sambo and Bwoi (2015), the job of the school principal in Nigeria has progressively become more complex and highly hazardous. In order to cope with the ever-rising challenges of the system, the school principal must be ready to see himself as a change agent.

The principal dictates the extent to which work is done in the school system (Abari and Mohammed 2018). The administrative leadership of the school principal is a critical factor in the success of a school's improvement initiatives and the overall effectiveness of the school. The primary responsibility of the principal is to promote the learning and success of all students (Lunenburg and Orstein 2008). It is against this background that the researcher decided to consider principals' administrative practice of instructional supervision in relation to teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Amirize and Ololube (2018) considered effective school administration as the achievement of a specific goal or aim of an educational institution. It is the attainment of the desired result through the utilization of the available resources. Usman (2016) viewed effective school administration as the implementation of programme geared towards the achievement of educational objectives through the utilization of the available resources. Considering definitions of Amirize and Ololube (2018) and Usman (2016), effective school administration could be considered as the successful attainment of predetermined educational objectives through utilization of the available resources.

According to Osakwe (2010), instructional supervision is concerned with the provision of professional assistance and guidance to teachers and students geared towards the achievement of effective teaching and learning in the school. The principal as a supervisor provides a professional guidance to teachers in order to improve their competencies for effective teaching process to enhance the learning and growth of the students. The school principal in carrying out their duties assist the teachers to perform effectively in the areas of preparation of lesson plan and lesson notes before lesson delivery, good use of instructional methods and teaching aids, keeping and maintaining of school records, classroom management, among others. Through supervision the principal can provide meaningful feedback and direction to teachers that can have profound effect in the learning that occurs in the classroom. Fritz and Miller (2003) opined that, the responsibility of ensuring that effective teaching and learning take place and the extent to which instructional supervisors carry out their duties is by employing various techniques to enhance teachers' job performance.

According to Jay (2014), teachers' job performance is the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes. Bolarinwa (2016) observes that, the indicator of teachers' job performance is

evaluated in the teachers' ability to make a deliberate effort to enhance students' academic performance, possession and display of in-depth knowledge of subject matter, lesson presentation, effective classroom organization and control, and participation in the school curriculum activities. Other indicators of teachers' job performance according to the author include regularity and punctuality in the school, maintenance of good interpersonal relationship with subordinates and superiors, discipline, motivation, and counselling of students as well as compliance to teachers' professional codes of conducts among others. In other words, teachers' job performance is the degree to which teachers successfully accomplish their instructional responsibilities. A teacher can be said to have performed when the teacher plans his/her lessons according to standards, delivers lessons comprehensively, manages the classroom well, uses instructional materials to facilitate teaching, carries out formative and summative assessments regularly, keep records of students' progress, participates in sporting activities as well as all other functions of the school for the attainment of the set goals of the school.

Efanga (2001) opines that teachers should establish effective classroom climate, students' motivation, management of materials and supplies, physical conditions for instruction, use of time, routines and a monitoring system in the classroom for efficient instruction and quality education. Also, Adeyemi (2011) asserted that variables of job performance such as teaching, lesson notes preparation, effective use of scheme of work, supervision, monitoring of students works and disciplinary ability are virtues that teachers are to uphold in a school system. Adeyemi further pointed out that, in this regard, the teachers' performance can be measured through annual reports of activities in terms of the above variables.

Teachers' job performance depends to a great extent on principals' administrative practices. Principals should try to equip their teachers with the skills that will ensure teachers' job performance and students' education goal attainment. Teachers are critical resources for effective implementation and realization of the educational policies and objectives at the practical level of the classroom. "It is the teacher who ultimately interprets and implements the policy as represented in school curriculum, which is designed to actualize educational goals" (Omojunwa, 2007). The obvious implication of this is the fact that principals must ensure that teachers do their jobs effectively.

This study is carried out to examine the extent to which principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The researcher took this decision considering the fact that, despite several attempt made by researchers to find solution to the problem of teachers' job performance using other independent variables like principals' personality, principals' traits, principals' academic qualification, principals' gender among others, the problem still persists in the public secondary schools.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Considering the belief of stakeholders at all levels that the country's education is in crisis, many researchers have taken steps to probe into problems related to the teaching and learning process. Despite the innumerable researches conducted and recommendations made with the intention of solving the problem of falling standard of education, most especially in the public secondary schools, this problem still persists. Accusing fingers from different quarters are therefore pointed to government, principals, teachers as well as students as being responsible for the decline in the standard of education.

Embarrassingly, professional laxity on the part of teachers has been observed to be the order of the day in public secondary schools. Some teachers are merely staying on the job to look for better jobs outside the education industry. Some are in the teaching profession simply because they have not got a job of their interest. As a result, consistent cases of defaulting in lesson preparation, persistent lateness to school and classes, irregular and unauthorized movement from duty post, failure to mark and correct students' work, non-utilization of instructional materials, inability to convincingly explain difficult concepts to students and above all, poor classroom management skill constitute a big problem to the attainment of educational goals in public secondary schools.

It becomes pertinent therefore to ask, "Could the lackadaisical attitude of teachers to their job performance be as a result of the principals' instructional supervision in the public secondary schools?" This question is apt because, teachers are the key drivers in the educational system and so, the success and /or failure of the system depends greatly on their effective job performance. It is against this background that the researcher decided to investigate how principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In other words, what is the extent to which principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The study was designed to examine the extent to which principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Question

To what extent does principals' instructional supervision practice predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

The extent to which principals' instructional supervision practice predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

1.6 Scope of Study

The scope of this study covered all the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria during the 2020/2021 academic year which ended in July 2021. The investigation centered on the principals' administrative practice of instructional supervision. Job performance of teachers were measured in terms of lesson preparation, lesson delivery, use of instructional materials, classroom management and students' evaluation in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Theoretical Framework.

2.1.1 Theory X and Theory Y- McGregor D. (1960)

Douglas McGregor developed his ideas of leadership theory and motivation in 1960. He compared two ideal-type of management philosophies along with assumptions which emerge from these views of human nature.

McGregor based his Theory X on assumption/prepositions generally associated with the conventional or efficiency views of management. The assumptions of the theory are:

- i. The average human being has an inherent dislike for work and will avoid it if possible.
- ii. Because of this human characteristic of dislike for work, most employees must be coerced, controlled, directed and threatened with punishment to get them to put forth adequate effort toward achieving organizational objectives.
- iii. The average human being prefers to be directed, wishes to avoid responsibilities, has relatively little ambition and wants security.

Theory Y's assumption represents a much more positive assessment of human behaviour. It was based on optimistic philosophy about human nature. McGregor's dissatisfaction with Theory X management and its assumptions' failure to consider certain human needs that relate to self-fulfilment, self-actualization, ego satisfaction and the social needs of man led him to formulate

Theory Y whose assumptions are:

- I. The expenditure of physical and mental efforts in work is as natural as play or rest.
- ii. External control and the threat of punishment are not only means of bringing about effort toward organizational objectives to which are committed.
- iii. Commitment to objectives is a function of the rewards associated with their achievement.
- iv. The average human being learns, under proper conditions, not only to accept but to seek responsibility.
- v. The capacity to exercise a relatively high degree of imagination, ingenuity and creativity in the solution of organizational problems is widely distributed

- in the population.
- vi. Under the conditions of modern industrial life, the intellectual potentialities of the average human being are only partially realized or utilized.

As principals strive to achieve the educational goals of the instructions, they tend to exhibit behaviour consistent with assumptions of the theories above. School principals who adopt the leadership style in line with Theory X are characterized by dictatorial procedures, eagerness for punitive measures against the subordinates and lack of participative management. The essence of the theory was a philosophy of direction closer supervision, external control and authoritarian and directive style of leadership. The implication of the assertion is that, a school principal who believed Theory X would always feel that average worker has inherent dislike for work and will eschew it if he can, and so must be coerced or forced to work. However, school principals who adopt the leadership style embedded in Theory Y are characterized by openness of communication with their subordinates; understanding and show concern for helping them develop and realize their potentials towards the achievement of common objectives. This theory is relevant to instructional supervision based on the fact that some teachers who are under the guidance of the principals deserve to be motivated, encouraged and carried along for the attainment of the goals of schools as stated in theory Y. On the contrary, there are also some of the teachers who look for the slightest excuse or opportunity to avoid their responsibilities as indicated by theory X of Douglas McGregor.

It is expedient that principals have to ensure that teachers are adequately supervised as stipulated in theory X to avoid laxity on their part. Likewise, theory Y advocates giving teachers a sense of belonging and working harmoniously with them in order to get the best of them in terms of job performance. Principals are therefore expected to carry out their instructional supervision duties in such manners that makes it evident that the intention is to help teachers to do their work well rather than finding faults in their duties.

2.2 Conceptual Review

According to Ekpoh and Eze (2015), teachers' job performance involves all the activities carried out by the teacher to achieve the desired effects on students. It involves the extent to which the teacher participates in the overall running of the school in order to achieve the expected objective and goals of the school. In other words, performance is the accomplishment of school goals.

Darling - Hammond (2010) defined an effective teacher as one who is intellectually challenging, motivating students, setting high standards and encourages self-initiating learning. Anderson (2007) viewed effective teachers as those teachers who achieved the goals set for them or goals set for them by others like the Ministry of Education. Effective teachers are very important for students learning. However, teachers' effectiveness is difficult to define since there has not been a consensus

agreement on what measured quality teacher (Stronge, Ward and Grant, 2011). However, it is possible to measure some teachers' attribute like interaction with student, teaching strategy, motivation, content knowledge and classroom management through qualitative research approach. These teachers' attributes could act in a long way to determine teachers' effectiveness.

Stronge *et al.* (2011), identified four dimensions that were used to characterize an effective teacher as follows: i. Instructional effectiveness. ii. Uses of assessment for student learning. iii. Positive learning environment. iv. Personal quality of the teacher.

An effective teaching should not only be concern with students' academic goals. Teachers' job performance should encompass concern for students' personal goals. Students enter into classroom from different background and they have come to the class with different mind apart from academic which an effective teacher should bear in mind. An effective teacher should always maximize instructional time and make good use of it. A teacher who wastes time in classroom discussing on irrelevant things is not effective.

Effective teacher especially in science make use of different type of technologies in his or her classroom (Aina, 2013). There are many applications of technologies in teaching and learning depending on the knowledge of the user (Nguyen, Williams and Nguyen 2012). The use of technologies is an imperative for all effective teachers in schools today. Moreover, effective teachers do not ignore complex concepts or topics in the curriculum but rather he or she will do everything possible as an effective teacher to ensure that such concepts are meaningful to the students.

Assessment and feedback is very important to students learning. Aina and Adedo (2013) found that feedback is very important in teaching and learning because it improve students' learning. Every effective teacher should know how, when and the type of assessment and feedback required in his or her lesson. We have different types of assessment, whichever form it might take, assessment activities take much time of the teachers and has an important place both in teachers and students' lives (Ceyhum and Erodogan, 2013).

Maintaining a positive environment for learning is the responsibility of an effective teacher. It is easy to distinguish between a teacher who is effective and the one who is not effective by the way they manage their classroom when lesson is going on. Managing classroom very well for Effective learning is the responsibility of an effective teacher. The ability of teachers to organize classrooms and manage the behaviour of their students is central to achieving good educational outcomes (Oliver and Reschly, 2007). Orji (2014) affirmed that effective teaching requires among other things basic management skill which include understanding of the nature of

classroom. Oliver and Reschly, (2007) cited Berliner that the teacher who has problems in classroom discipline is frequently ineffective in classroom.

An effective teacher will always interact well with students both within and outside the classroom because this is very important to students' learning. Interaction between teacher and student in school is very important and effective teachers should ensure maximum interaction that will enhance learning in the classroom. Interest and achievement of students lie within the teacher and students' interaction/relationship in a given subject (Onah and Ugwu, 2010). Creating classroom Environments that promote positive cultures with healthy interactions can motivate students to channel their energies and desires to reach their goals (Nugent, 2009). Teacher students' interaction is very important in school as it aid students' success. The interaction between teachers and students is essentially the fundamental basis for teaching. A good teacher student relationship may be even more valuable for students with behaviour and learning challenges (Caballero, 2010). Most students learn best in the environment where they are able to freely express their feeling and this could be a situation when they are free with the teacher.

Knoell (2012) agreed that learning occurs best in an environment that contains positive interpersonal relationships and interactions and in which learner feel appreciated, acknowledged, respected and admired. Students who enjoy a close and supportive relationship with a teacher are more engaged and work harder in the classroom, persistence in the face of difficulties and cope better with stress. Apart from those attribute of teachers' effectiveness mentioned above, others that are very important in measuring teachers' effectiveness are motivation, content knowledge and students' homework. Motivation could act as a catalyst for many science Students who have lost interest in the course, may be because of the abstract nature of the subject (Adeyemo, 2010; Aina, 2013) or because of teachers' poor strategies of teaching (Wanbugu, Johnson and Francis, 2013).

According to Christiana (2009), motivation is very important to students' learning. Where this motivation is lacking because of teachers' ineffectiveness the result is always not good. Teacher job performance in classroom is very important and where a teacher is not effective in teaching, students' academic performance will be poor. The importance of teacher job performance must not be toyed with and that is the more reason it is not appropriate to employ unqualified teacher to schools. Any effective teacher should know the importance of homework in teaching and learning and should ensure he/she regularly administers it to the students. Homework is recognized as one indicator of successful schools and successful students. Teacher should design homework that is more effective and encouraging which allows low ability students to complete at the given time (Epstein and Voorhis, 2001).

2.2.2 Principals' Instructional Supervision and Teachers' Job Performance

The Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2013) identified management of curriculum and instruction, supervision of classroom instruction, monitoring and evaluating students' progress and achievement, promoting and enhancing learning environment, establishing and supporting continuous staff development and procuring instructional materials for teaching and learning as major supervisory functions of secondary school principals. The educational policy also makes it clear that one of the cardinal objectives of administration in education is to ensure quality control through regular and continuous supervision of instruction and other educational services.

Classroom observation is a valuable tool which is employed to understand classroom realities and achieve high standards of effective teaching methodologies. For instance, it offers an opportunity for supervisors to assess teachers' styles, their classroom management skills and various aspects of teaching that are hard to obtain through other forms of evaluation. Moreover, it allows teachers to receive constructive feedback on their teaching techniques and methods in a bid to improve them further. In a nutshell, it is one of the most common ways of reflecting on instructional practices (Farrell, 2011), which can help teachers evaluate their strengths and weaknesses.

Oyewole and Ehinola (2014) opined that the primary purpose of supervision in Nigerian schools is to improve instructional programme. The authors identified three categories of teachers to whom supervisory assistance should be directed. They are:

- I. New teachers, (who are fresh from school and so need encouragement and support in their new profession in order to achieve the stated goals).
- ii. Old teachers (who attempt to resist change because they have been used to certain styles of teaching, hence, they consider change as a threat).
- iii. Incompetent teachers (because of their shallow knowledge of subject matter, poor classroom organization, ineffective use of language, etc)

Ezedi (2002) said that instructional supervision strategies in the school organizational framework should analytically examine the following variables closely on the regular basis.

- i. Teacher Service: Regularity/punctuality, weekly lesson preparation, coverage of work schedules and documentation of pupils' work.
- ii. Pupils learning effort: Regularity and punctuality of classes, completion of assignments, achievements and conduct scores.
- iii. Curriculum benefits: Adequacy of textbooks and their uses, relevance of continuous assessment and guidance counseling in the school system.
- iv. School facilities: Adequate sanitation and maintenance of accommodation facilities (classrooms, laboratories, library, halls, offices etc) equipment and supplies.

According to Dull (2003), the modern concept of instructional supervision therefore, expects the principal to play the following roles: (i) Visit classroom regularly to observe teachers. (ii) Organize conference with teachers collectively and individually to discuss ways of improving instruction for effective learning. (iii) Teach demonstration lessons. (iv) Organize induction courses for newly posted and recruited teachers. (v) Ensure that instructional goals are achieved. (vi) Ensure that instructional materials are available. (vii) Help teachers with classroom management. (viii) Inculcate in students the idea that they have understanding potential for achievement. (ix) Evaluate teachers' effort in relation to the schools pre-determined objectives. (x) Motivate and lead teacher into professional maturity.

To carry out a successful and harmonious classroom visitation, Ekpoh and Eze (2015) advocated the following strategies:

- I. Existence of good rapport between teachers and supervisor, so that the latter would not be seen as an enemy.
- ii. The supervisor should carefully prepare the visit and should enter the classroom as unobtrusively as possible.
- iii. A conference should precede and follow the visit.
- iv. The supervisor should concentrate on the total learning situation, students – teacher behaviour and the attitude of the students.
- v. Visitation should be at the approval of the teacher.
- vi. The supervisor should attempt to discover strong points in the learning situation, discuss the past during conference and give credit where it is due.
- vii. The supervisor should never openly show disapproval of what happens in the classroom, rather, should make complimentary remarks before leaving the classroom.

The principal as an instructional leader is responsible for maintaining and improving the quality of instructional programmes for the effective and efficient attainment of the set educational objectives of the school. Litchfield (2003) identified the functions of the school principal as an instructional leader. These functions include supervision of classroom instruction, among other functions. Supervising classroom instruction involves the principal observing a teacher and analysing his or her classroom practice and the teaching and learning process. This is a situation where the teacher is working directly with the learners and the principal is present as a witness to observe systematically classroom events.

According to Igwe (2001) classroom visitation is a procedure by which the instructional leader who possesses wisdom can be of great assistance in aiding the teacher to improve both his instructional techniques and the learning process of the student. According to Peretomode(2001), classroom visitation is a procedure by which the educational leader could be of great assistance in aiding the teachers to improve both their instructional strategies/techniques and the learning processes of the students. It is often used to provide teachers with constructive critical feedback

aimed at improving their classroom management and instructional techniques. The principal has to be a visionary who leads the school community to use teaching and curricular strategies that are more effective and also support teachers' effort to implement effective instruction. Classroom visitation/observation is one supervisory skill that the principal must use if he plans to achieve effective teaching and learning in the school. Classroom visitation is not a situation whereby the expert visits the class discovers what is wrong and then directs the teacher to change certain methods of teaching but a process wherein the principal learns or observes what is going on in the classroom in order to be helpful to the teachers. The principal through classroom visitation may discover things that will help in teachers' job performance. The principal can also learn things that could make him or her better administrator.

Classroom observation has two concerns: To teach the lesson so well; or as well as possible and to invent or document the occurring during the lesson as accurately as possible. Classroom visitation could be done in three different ways, namely: i. by invitation ii. announced visitation iii. un-announced visitation

The instructional leader should be able to choose the appropriate method depending on the situation. The observer should position himself or herself at the back of the classroom and be as non-intrusive as possible. During the class, the supervisor should note such things as the relationship the teacher has with their students, the learning environment, student participation, teaching methodologies, organization and presentation of the material. When teachers are not well supervised, effectiveness in instruction will be adversely affected and the instructional purposes may not be realized. Wayne (2017) gave tips for conducting better classroom visitation as: Prepare yourself and prepare the teacher, look for learning, not teaching, properly judge the lesson plan, tie your observation to the professional learning at your school and Give feedback promptly.

According to Peretomode (2001), classroom visitation is a procedure by which the instructional leader could be of great assistance in aiding the teachers to improve both their instructional strategies/techniques and the learning processes of the student. The main objective of the principals' visitation according to the definition is for the improvement of the teaching-learning process.

Shantz and Ward (2000) observed that for teachers to improve instructional delivery, they rely on feedback given to them by supervisors. Constructive criticism and guidance giving by supervising teachers are important in helping teachers develop their teaching proficiency and consequently achieving effective learning on the part of the students. Rettig (2000) noted that instructional activities foster teacher motivation, inspiration, trust, and help to improve teaching performance. As a result, it may be reasonable to expect a positive relationship to exist certain aspects of instructional supervision and effective learning. The effectiveness of the school is largely dependent on the principal's ability to supervise the teachers to clarify

instructional goals and work collaboratively to improve teaching and learning. (Blasé, Blasé and Philips, 2010)

According to Daniel and Namale (2016), inadequate time spent on supervision by supervisors is one of the key challenges due to multiple roles that the supervisors have to perform as part of their administrative duties. Dali, Daud and Fauzee (2017) concurring with Daniel and Namale explain that there are a number of roles which the principal has to undertake in a school, some of which do not add value. According to Dali et al. (2017), some of these roles should either be delegated or done away with.

Daniel and Namale also observe teachers' negative attitude as one of the main inhibitors to instructional supervision which they refer to as teacher resistance to evaluation. Dali et al. (2017) argued that the attitude of teachers towards instructional supervisors most likely depends on the approach and type of instructional supervision offered at a given stage. They give an example of fault-finding and evaluative approach both of which they maintain are most likely to result in teachers viewing supervision negatively and as a result creating lack of trust in supervision undertaken by the supervisor. The negative attitude and dissatisfaction of teachers toward instructional supervision also depends on the supervisor-teacher relationship as well as methods and approaches of supervision used in order to assist teachers' needs.

Lack of good supervisor teacher relationship causes a great challenge to effective instructional supervision (Yelkpieri and Namale, 2016). According to De Grauwe (2007), bitter complaints about supervisor's work including irregular and bad planning of visits, inadequate time spent in the classroom on supervision, and inappropriate advice offered by supervisors, are among the key issues in instructional supervision characterized by negative attitude by teachers' on the exercise. The authors also note and warned that teachers strongly dislike the classic fault finding approach by the supervisors, and that teachers expect to be treated as professionals and the specific realities of the school environment be taken into account when supervisors provide advice during their supervisory visits.

Egwu (2015) suggests that teachers tend not to favour individualized and unsupportive instructional supervision which does not address their individual needs. They further argue that teachers disagree with instructional supervision that recommends change, which they believe is not possible in their classroom behaviour. Darling-Hammond (2010) believes that instructional supervisors should use specified, measurable outcomes as an evaluation tool. This approach plays a major role in supervision as it describes and highlights the teaching and learning that happens each day in the classroom, without focusing on how a teacher measures up to the standards required. Knight and Nieuwerburgh (2012) concur with Darling-Hammond (2010) and proceed to argue that, while addressing instructional supervision that improves teaching, the focus of instructional supervision especially

in the area of clinical supervision should be on the actual classroom practices that ensure the process is of practical significance to the teacher, based on self-direction and self-confidence, but not on measurable outcomes which promotes resistance from teachers.

According to Wanzare (2013) and Tshabalala (2013), poor, inadequate and sometimes lack of communication between teachers and instructional supervisors, is also a major inhibitor to instructional supervision. The authors further note that, when instructional supervisors and teachers perceive supervision differently there is bound to be friction and conflict emanating from the exercise. In contrast, when an instructional supervisor and a teacher make decisions objectively on the approach on instructional supervision together as colleagues, there is more likely to be mutual agreement. This phase of supervision is seen as the most challenging and one that other problems arise from (Glickman, Gordon and Ross-Gordon 2017). Archibong (2012) echoes Wanzare (2011) on poor communication and explains that lack of adequate communication between instructional supervisors and teachers contribute significantly to failure in instructional supervision.

Some teachers feel that supervision is an intrusion into their private instructional practices. They claim that the principal's intrusive monitoring and physical presence change the setting in the classrooms and that this results in false impressions resulting in an element of stress and overreaction, on the part of the teachers and the students during classroom observations.

Knowledge and experience also play an important role in instructional supervision and characterizes most increasing issues and several challenges that emanate from discharging instructional supervisory services, including the possession of some working experiences that enable the supervisor to provide the necessary assistance, guidance, and support services to teachers for quality classroom instructions (Holland, 2005). Holland is particularly more categorical that instructional supervisors must show evidence that they have the necessary knowledge and experience to make important decisions about instructions. In addition, the author argues that the instructional supervisor must also show evidence in the form of degrees and diplomas, so as to inspire teachers' trust.

According to Nzabonimpa (2009), instructional supervisors lack time for effective instructional supervision, partly due to overload of work caused by many other responsibilities that instructional supervisors are expected to perform. Adul, Akinloye and Olabisi. (2014) argued that, "it is the administration that has failed to specify the scope of responsibilities and results instructional supervision is expected to bring about in the school". In support of the authors, Enaigbe (2009) confirms that the instructional supervisors are responsible for carrying out school based instructional supervision in addition to routine administrative tasks. Enaigbe further argues that, supervisors are overwhelmed by routine administrative burden that they

hardly find time to visit classrooms and observe how the teachers perform in classrooms. Wanzare (2013) adds his voice and comments that the instructional supervisor's excessive workload has direct bearing on the negative effects in the practice of supervision. He further posits that, when a choice is made between administrative and pedagogical duties, the latter suffers.

2.3 Empirical Framework

2.3.1 Principals' Instructional Supervision

Ampofo, Onyango, and Ogola, (2019) assessed the influence of school heads' direct supervision on teacher role performance in public senior high schools. The study adopted the embedded mixed methods design. Slovin's formula, the proportional allocation method, and simple random and purposive sampling were used to select a sample of 617 respondents comprising 295 teachers, 222 class prefects, 86 Heads of Department, 13 school heads and 1 Regional Director for the Inspectorate Division of the Ghana Education Service. Data were collected through questionnaires and interview guides. Quantitative data were analyzed using frequencies, means and multiple regression whereas patterns and themes were developed for the analysis of qualitative data. The study found that school heads allocated very little time for supervision of lesson planning and delivery of teachers. The study established that school heads' lesson planning supervision ($p= 0.043 < .05$) and lesson delivery supervision ($p= .035 < .05$) had a significant influence on teacher role performance. Therefore, the study recommends the Ghana Education Service to dedicate a greater portion of the promotion requirement of the school heads to evidence of direct supervision of teachers and a reduction in the teaching load of Heads of Department by the school head to enable them play more instrumental roles in the instructional supervision process. The finding of this research indicates that school principals dedicate little time to instructional supervision in terms of lesson planning and delivery. The implication of this is that should more time be given to instructional supervision, the job performance of teachers will be better.

Atieno (2019) carried out a study which aimed at establishing the performance of principals in their instructional supervisory role with regard to enhancing teacher professional development. The objectives of the study were to establish the effectiveness of principals' instructional supervision as perceived by the principals themselves, heads of departments and teachers in public secondary schools; identify challenges faced by principals in undertaking instructional supervisory role in public secondary schools; establish how instructional supervision has enhanced teacher professional development in public secondary schools; examine the strategies used by principals to enhance instructional supervision in public secondary schools. This study adopted Developmental Supervision Theory by Glickman et al. Descriptive survey design which embraces both quantitative and qualitative approaches, was used. The study was carried out in public secondary schools in Nairobi and Kajiado counties in Kenya. The sample size was as follows: 38 principals, 151 heads of departments and 289 teachers. This gave a sample size of 478 respondents. Stratified

random sampling was used in selecting schools according to the following strata: boys' public secondary schools, girls' public secondary schools and mixed public secondary schools. Simple random sampling was used to select heads of departments and teachers for the study.

The instruments used to collect data were: Questionnaire for principals, heads of departments and teachers. There was also an Interview guide for principals. Content validity was determined by seeking expert judgment from specialists in the department of educational management, policy and curriculum studies; while the reliability of the instruments was ascertained by using Cronbach's alpha technique. Qualitative data was analyzed thematically, while Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and presented in frequencies and percentages. Null hypotheses were analyzed using Kruskal-Wallis H test statistics. The key finding of this study was that majority of principals' performed diligently but did not use appropriate skills or lacked knowledge on how to conduct effective instructional supervision. The finding also established that lack of funds hindered the extent to which principals performed in enhancing teachers' professional development. Based on the findings, the study recommends the need for TSC to introduce a policy on instructional supervision so that the principals who are selected to head schools can gain skills and knowledge to enable them effectively perform their tasks and responsibilities related to instructional supervision. Secondly, adequate funds should be allocated for in-service courses, seminars and workshops in order to improve teachers' professional development. The implication of the findings of this study is that if principals can apply the expected instructional supervision skills appropriately, their administrative practice will be effective and the job performance of teachers will improve.

Iroegbu and Etudor-Eyo (2016) examined the differences in teachers' effectiveness based on principals' instructional supervision in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Education Committee in Akwa Ibom State. Four objectives and their corresponding research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The ex-post facto design was used in carrying out this study. Two hundred and one teachers and 14 principals were drawn from the population of 1,105 teachers and 14 principals respectively to participate in the study. Two researchers-developed instruments, "Principals' Instructional Supervision Interview (PIS1)" and "Teachers' Teaching Effectiveness Questionnaire (TTEQ)" were used to gather data. Data collected were analyzed using the mean and independent t-test statistics was used. The findings were that there is a significant difference in teachers' effectiveness based on classroom observation, analysis/strategy, post-conference analysis and post-analysis conference. Teachers in schools where instructional supervision was adequate were more effective than those that had inadequate instructional supervision. It is, therefore, recommended among others that, the principals should carry out an adequate instructional supervision of teachers so as to enhance their teaching effectiveness. The finding of this work suggest that if all the principals can

be actively involved in instructional supervision, all the teachers in the public secondary schools will do their job well.

Paul, David, John and Musaazi (2016) investigated the effect of instructional supervision by school authorities on the pedagogical practices of teachers in public secondary schools in Uganda. The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional survey design, in which both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection and analysis were applied. Study respondents included 934 teachers randomly selected from 95 public secondary schools, 76 head teachers, and two officials from the Directorate of Education Standards of the Ministry of Education and Sports. Ordered logistic regression technique was used to establish the effect of instructional supervision on the pedagogical practices of teachers. Findings of the study revealed that both classroom observation (odd ratio=4.1; $p=0.000<0.05$) and portfolio supervision (odd ratio=2.3; $p=0.000<0.05$) have statistically significant effect on the pedagogical practices of teachers in public secondary schools in Uganda. Furthermore, the study established that school authorities were inadequately carrying out instructional supervision, thereby leaving teachers to employ ineffective pedagogical practices. The study concluded that teachers' pedagogical practices are dependent on the manner in which they are supervised, other factor notwithstanding. Therefore, in order to augment the pedagogical practices of teachers, school inspection by the Directorate of Education Standards should be increased and regular in-service training needs to be provided to head teachers as well as subject heads on how to conduct classroom observations and portfolio supervision in schools. The relationship between this study and the current research is that this study opined that poor teachers' job performance is as a result of inadequate instructional supervision.

Ekpoh and Eze (2015) investigated the relationship between principals' supervisory techniques and teachers' job performance in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The sample was 86 principals, 344 teachers and 1,376 students drawn from a population of 86 principals, 1829 teachers and 35,359 students in public secondary schools in the study area. To achieve the purpose of the study, two null hypotheses were formulated. Data collection was carried out with the use of two research instruments titled "Principals' Supervisory Technique Questionnaire (PSTQ)" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)". The instruments were subjected to face validity and Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate. The reliability value obtained ranged between 0.73 and 0.78. These figures confirmed that the instruments were reliable in achieving the objective of the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis (r) was used for data analysis at .05 level of significance. Results obtained revealed that a significant relationship exist between principals' supervisory techniques in terms of classroom visitation, workshop techniques and teachers' job performance. Based on the findings, it was concluded that job performances of teachers would be enhanced when they are properly supervised by principals using the various supervisory techniques. The current research is related to this study

because the researchers postulate that there will be better job performance on the part of teachers if there is adequate instructional supervision.

Sule (2013) investigated the influence of principal's supervisory demonstration strategy on teachers' job performance in Cross River State, Nigeria. Respondents involved six hundred and sixty (660) teachers and three thousand, three hundred senior secondary school students which were randomly selected from two hundred and thirty-two (232) secondary schools in Cross River State. Data was collected with Principals' Instructional Supervisory Strategies Questionnaire (PISSQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Scale Questionnaire (TJPSQ). The result of analysis utilizing one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicated that principal's demonstration strategy did not significantly influence teachers' job performance. It is recommended that regular supervision should be organized by the Ministry of Education using more robust supervisory strategies which may include classroom visitation and inspection, inspection of teachers' lesson notes, conferencing strategy, inspection of teachers' record keeping, and administrative workshop strategy. This study and the current research are related because the researchers recommended that instructional supervision should be carried out regularly if a better teachers' job performance is desired.

Egbe (2010) researched on principals' instructional supervision and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Calabar municipal council of Cross River State. The population of the study consisted of 1,200 SSII students and 277 teachers. This made a total population size of 1,477. Two instruments called "Questionnaire for Teacher Effectiveness (QTE)" for students were developed for data collection. The data collected were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) for testing the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' effectiveness in lesson presentation. The relationship between this study and the current research is that the researcher found out that lesson presentation (delivery) is an aspect of instructional supervision that leads to improved teachers' job performance.

Sule, Ameh and Egbai (2015) investigated the relationship between instructional supervisory practices and teachers' role effectiveness in public secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprises all public secondary school principals and teachers in the study area. There are a total of six (6) principals and four hundred and thirty-three (433) teachers. Simple random sampling technique was used to select one hundred and ninety-five (195) teachers from six (6) public secondary schools. A well-structured questionnaire tagged "Instructional Supervisory Practices Questionnaire (ISPQ) and Teachers' Role Effectiveness Questionnaire (TREQ)" were used for data collection. The results of the analysis revealed that there was a

significant positive relationship between instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation and teachers' role effectiveness. The result also revealed that, there was a significant positive relationship between instructional supervisory practice of checking of teachers' lesson notes and teachers' role effectiveness. It was concluded that a closer, regular and continuous instructional supervisory practice rather than snappy, unscheduled and partial supervision is what is urgently needed especially now that a lot of changes have been introduced into the school curriculum. It was recommended among others that Government through the Ministry of Education should organize training programmes for principals as well as teachers on the need for effective instructional supervision. The implication of this study is that the more effective and regular instructional supervision is carried out, the better teachers' job performance becomes.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of the 254 public secondary school principals and all the 7388 teachers of the public secondary schools in the three Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State.

3.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was 739 teachers from the three senatorial districts (the thirty-three Local Government Area) which formed 10% of teachers of Akwa Ibom State. The sample was selected through the clustered sampling technique where the state was grouped into the three Senatorial Districts. 10% of the total number of teachers in each of the three Senatorial Districts was further selected as sample through simple random sampling. Three students were also randomly selected to provide information on each teacher's job performance from each of the three Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom.

3.3 Instrumentation

Two instruments named Principals' Administrative Practices Questionnaire (PAPQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were used to collect data from respondents (Teachers and students)

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data generated in this study were analyzed using Simple Linear Regression analysis for research questions and null hypotheses. The hypothesis was tested at a .05 level of significance.

4.0 Empirical Result

4.1 Answering the Research Question

Research Question: To what extent does principals' instructional supervision predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

To answer this research question, Simple Linear Regression analysis was employed, and the data obtained is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis for the extent to which principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary school in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Variable	R	R-squared	Extent of Prediction	Remarks
Principals' Institutional Supervision (X)	0.750	0.563	56.3%	Moderate Extent
Teachers' Job Performance (Y)				

Source: Researcher Computation (2022)

The entry in Table 1 reveals the R for the strength of the relationship and R^2 for the determination of the extent to which principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance. The R- Value of .750 indicates the extent to which the prediction occurs. The calculated R^2 of .563 which is the coefficient of determinant indicates that only 56.3% variability in effectiveness is predicted or contributed by principals' instructional supervision. This implies that principals' instructional supervision to a moderate extent, predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.2 Testing the research Hypothesis

Hypothesis: - The extent to which principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

Table 2: Simple linear regression analysis for the prediction between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom (df)	Mean Square	F-Cal	Significance
Regression	86579.268	1	86579.268	946.561	0.000 ^b
Residual	67228.354	735	91.467		
Total	153807.62	736			

Source: Researcher Computation (2022)

The entries in Table 2 revealed that the calculated F-value of 946.56 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at .05 level of significant with 1 and 736 degree of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which claims that the extent to which principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job performance is not significant is rejected. The result reveals that principals' instructional supervision significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary school in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.3 Findings

The findings of the study indicated that Principals' instructional supervision significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The result shows that there is significant prediction between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This result means that principals' ability to ensure that teachers to teach lessons according to the time table, observe teachers during lessons, instruct teachers to manage classroom effectively, insist that students' works are checked regularly and conduct follow-up visit to classroom contributes to a moderate extent to teachers' job performance in the area of lesson delivery, classroom management and students' assessment. This is in line with the opinion of Sergiovanni and Starratt (2007) that, "principals' instructional supervision focuses primarily on helping teachers reflect on their actions and promoting school improvement through professional development". Likewise, Chen and Chen (2013), asserted that, to positively affect teachers' quality, principals must engage teachers in ways that support improved practice and seek to empower teachers as creative and innovative.

To support the finding of this study, Yelkper and Namale (2016) pointed out that lack of good supervisor- teacher relationship causes a great challenge to effective instructional supervision. Moreover, Ampofo, Onyango, and Ogola, (2019) opined that because school heads' spend little or no time on direct supervision of instruction, teachers' job performance in public senior high schools keeps declining. This finding is also in line with Atieno (2019) who stated that some principals lacked knowledge on how to conduct effective instructional supervision, therefore, there should be introduction of a policy on instructional supervision so that the principals who are selected to head schools can gain skills and knowledge to enable them effectively perform their tasks and responsibilities related to instructional supervision.

Iroegbu and Etudor-Eyo (2016) emphasized that principals should carry out adequate instructional supervision of teachers so as to enhance their teaching effectiveness. In like manner, Paul, David, John and Musaaazi (2016) established that when school authorities inadequately carrying out instructional supervision in public secondary schools, teachers may employ ineffective instructional practices because

teachers' instructional practices are dependent on the manner in which they are supervised, other factor notwithstanding.

Ekpoh and Eze (2015) concluded that job performance of teachers would be enhanced when they are properly supervised by principals using the various supervisory techniques. Sule (2013) emphasizing on the relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job performance recommended that regular supervision should be organized by the Ministry of Education using more robust supervisory strategies which may include classroom visitation and inspection, inspection of teachers' lesson notes, conferencing strategy, inspection of teachers' record keeping, and administrative workshop strategy.

Sule, Arop and Alade (2012) in support of the finding of this study stated that when the process of delivering the educational service is monitored, checked, encouraged and improved for efficiency and effectiveness, the end product would be of high quality. The researchers also opined that the feedback or data derived from classroom visitation/observation would help the principal to re-plan, adjust and improve where necessary. Likewise, Egbe (2010) revealed that there is a significant relationship between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' effectiveness in lesson presentation. Sule, Ameh and Egbai (2015) revealed that, a closer, regular and continuous instructional supervisory practice rather than snappy, unscheduled and partial supervision is what is urgently needed especially now that a lot of changes have been introduced into the school curriculum. In summary, the aims of instructional supervision is to provide objective feedback to teachers; diagnose and solve teaching problems; help teachers develop their strategies and skills; evaluate teachers for promotions or appointments; and to help teachers maintain a positive attitude (Jared, 2011). A principal who is unwilling to perform skilful instructional supervision that supports improved teaching and positive interactions risks diminished trust (Adams, 2007).

5 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended among other things that principals should ensure that they personally conduct instructional supervision from time to time to be sure that there is a check on the effectiveness of instructional supervision carried out by the vice principals and heads of departments. Likewise, the Ministry of Education and State Secondary Education Board should as a matter of priority ensure that principals who are appointed to head schools have the administrative leadership capacities for smooth and effective supervision of the public secondary schools' teachers. It is also recommended that the state government through the Ministry of Education should ensure that school facilities, qualified personnel as well as instructional materials are adequately provided in the public secondary schools.

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